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Additional Information

Coordinated Dual-hormone Artificial Pancreas with Parallel Control Structure

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Abstract

Concomitant glucagon delivery in a dual-hormone artificial pancreas system might overcome the limitations of insulin-only systems, potentially leading to improved hypoglycemia mitigation. However, current dual-hormone systems have not shown clearly its superiority. This work presents a novel dual-hormone system based on a parallel control structure with intrinsic coordination among insulin and glucagon delivery. The proposed coordinated controller (CC) was compared with its non-coordinated counterpart (NCC) based on independent loops for the insulin and glucagon controllers, as done in current systems. To evaluate the benefits of coordination, CC and NCC shared the same insulin controller, differing solely on how glucagon is administered. An in-silico study using the UVA-Padova simulator, extended with variability sources, was performed. Three scenarios were considered, comprising meals, snacks and exercise. CC achieved superior performance with better values of times in ranges. Moreover, CC delivered lower glucagon doses than the two NCC tuning alternatives considered.

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1. Introduction

People with type 1 diabetes (T1D) lack the ability to secrete insulin and therefore are unable to regulate their blood glucose endogenously. Several technologies have been developed to maintain normoglycemia in patients by means of exogenous insulin delivery (e.g. Multiple Daily Injections -MDI- with insulin pens or Continuous Subcutaneous Insulin Infusion -CSII- with insulin pumps). Nevertheless, achieving a good glucose control can be extremely difficult for patients due to factors like physiological variability, large glycemic impact of disturbances like exercise and meals, whose carbohydrate content must be estimated by the patient, and delays in subcutaneous insulin delivery compared to pancreatic secretion, among others (Haidar, 2016; Kudva et al., 2014; Scavone et al., 2010; Hovorka, 2006; Riddell et al., 2015). For this reason, to achieve better glycemic control and quality of life for people with T1D, there has been a worldwide effort to develop an automated (closed-loop) glucose control system, known as the “artificial pancreas” (AP). A single-hormone AP system uses a continuous glucose monitor (CGM), an insulin pump and a control algorithm to modulate insulin delivery at each sampling period (commonly 5 minutes). It has been demonstrated that achieving near-normoglycemia reduces the risk for long-term diabetic complications (Nathan et al., 2005). Nevertheless, intensive insulin treatment, including the artificial pancreas, can increase the risk of hypoglycemia with potentially severe complications including coma or death. In the design of the AP control algorithm, this problem has been addressed principally from two different perspectives, not mutually-exclusive: (1) the incorporation of mechanisms for insulin-on-board (IOB) limitation, i.e., the active insulin in the body that will have an effect later (only option in a single-hormone system) (Ellingsen et al., 2009; Revert et al., 2013); and (2) the introduction of dual-hormone artificial pancreas systems which infuse glucagon as counterregulatory action to increase plasma glucose (El-Khatib et al., 2010; Castle et al., 2010;

Haidar et al., 2013b; Herrero et al., 2012).

30 Current dual-hormone systems are based on two control loops with an insulin controller and a glucagon controller. This latter is activated in certain circumstances with the goal of triggering a counterregulatory control action to mitigate hypoglycemia. It has been commonly thought that dual-hormone systems may allow being more aggressive with the insulin infusion compared to
35 a single hormone system since it is possible to modulate the excessive insulin action with the glucagon infusion. However, recent studies demonstrate that the excess of insulinemia could reduce the glucagon effectiveness and have effect on hypoglycaemia incidence (El Youssef et al., 2014).

The viability of the dual-hormone AP in humans was demonstrated in (El-
40 Khatib et al., 2010). The system incorporated a Model Predictive Control (MPC) controller for insulin infusion and a Proportional-Derivative (PD) controller for glucagon infusion, which was activated only when glycemia was lower than the target threshold or the glycaemic descent speed was greater than a certain value. Other examples of this kind of configuration are presented in (Castle
45 et al., 2010) with a fading memory PD controller for insulin and glucagon infusion. In (Haidar et al., 2013b) an MPC controller was used for the insulin infusion with constraints based on the glucagon-on-board (analogous concept to IOB) and glucagon bolus administration following heuristic rules. Finally, other approaches included the use of a bio-inspired controller for insulin delivery
50 combined with a PD controller for the glucagon delivery (Herrero et al., 2012).

The current clinical evaluations have not successfully demonstrated the expected superiority of dual-hormone systems compared with single-hormone ones with a similar hypoglycemia incidence in general (Haidar et al., 2016). During the overnight control especially, the single-hormone systems were sufficient to
55 achieve an efficient control (Haidar et al., 2015). However, the dual-hormone systems showed better results during studies with exercise (Taleb et al., 2016). Besides, Castle et al. (2018) demonstrated recently that the addition of glucagon delivery to the closed-loop system with automatic exercise detection reduces hypoglycemia after aerobic exercise.

60 Physiologically, there is communication between the beta and alpha cells,
responsible for the insulin and glucagon secretion, respectively (Jain and Lam-
mert, 2009). In (Cooperberg and Cryer, 2009) it is demonstrated that an incre-
ment in plasma insulin levels produces a suppression in glucagon secretion in
T1D patients, and a decrement in insulin levels with low plasma glucose con-
65 centrations stimulates glucagon secretion. Furthermore, authors in (Rodriguez-
Diaz et al., 2011) showed that the alpha cell anticipates the possible hyper-
glycemic rebounds due to the glucagon secretion by means of beta cell stimu-
lation. It was observed that there is paracrine communication in both direc-
tions. Thus, coordination between the secretion of both hormones is a relevant
70 factor to take into account in the glycemic control. In a recent work, a coordi-
nated biologically-inspired glucose control strategy was presented (Herrero et al.,
2017), achieving a reduction of hyperglycemia without increasing hypoglycemia
when compared to its non-coordinated configuration. However, efficient hypo-
glycemia mitigation in dual-hormone systems is still an open issue.

75 For this reason, the objective of this work is the assessment of a new dual-
hormone control algorithm with intrinsic insulin and glucagon coordination,
based on a collaborative parallel control formulation for multiple-input single-
output (MISO) plants, in order to improve AP performance. A comparison
with its non-coordinated counterpart has been carried out to investigate the
80 benefits of the proposed coordination scheme as opposed to current approaches
in dual-hormone AP systems.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents the coordinated control
strategy used in the controller proposed, the non-coordinated structure used as
comparator, and the tuning of both of them; Section 3 shows the results of the
85 simulations for the considered scenarios for each control scheme besides of a
posterior comparison and discussion about them; finally, conclusions are drawn
in Section 4.

2. Methods

2.1. Coordinated control strategy

90 The dual-hormone AP control problem can be casted as the design of a controller for a MISO plant, with insulin and glucagon infusion as plant inputs and glucose as output. Control strategies for this class of plants are numerous and can be classified as “non-collaborative” and “collaborative” (Rico-Azagra et al., 2014). In noncollaborative control strategies, a selector splits online the
95 control action to the plant input channel with capability to regulate the output at the current operating point, converting the design into a set of single-input single-output (SISO) control design problems. On the contrary, collaborative control strategies aim at improving the performance of the system taking benefit of the dynamic characteristics of each plant input channel, considering the
100 restrictions of the manipulated variables. This approach has been developed in different ways in literature (see (Rico-Azagra et al., 2014) for an enumeration). Of relevance to this work is the concept introduced in the so-called “habituating control” (Henson et al., 1995; McLain et al., 1996), inspired by the physiology of blood pressure control, where control actions are classified as
105 “slow and cheap” (the primary control action) and “fast and expensive” (the secondary control action). In this case, the “fast and expensive” action, much more efficient, acts at a first stage, giving way (“habituating”) to the “slow and cheap” action which ultimately achieves the control objective (Henson et al., 1995). In a dual-hormone AP systems, there naturally arises the analogy of
110 the “fast and expensive” control action with glucagon, which presents a faster subcutaneous pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, but, its delivery must be constrained to 1 mg/day due to the possible side effects. This restriction implies that the use of glucagon must be as low as possible, determining that the use of this hormone must be considered as the “expensive”. On the other hand,
115 the “slow and cheap” action is associated with insulin. Glucagon can respond quickly when hypoglycemia occurs while insulin decreases to produce a latest effect on plasma glucose concentrations. Besides, glucagon may ultimately act

as a secondary control action when insulin is saturated (insulin infusion cannot have negative values) or insulin delivery is below a given threshold for hypoglycemia mitigation. Overall, the control effort provided by the combined action of insulin and glucagon must be the one needed to maintain the glucose control targets. To this end, the general parallel control structure in Figure 1 is proposed in this work, as opposed to independent control loops for insulin and glucagon as used in current systems. A master controller computes a virtual control action representing a control effort, which is then distributed among insulin and glucagon according to given logics leading to a coordinated hormones delivery.

Figure 1: General block diagram of the parallel control structure applied to the dual-hormone artificial pancreas system.

The design of the control system in Figure 1 is adapted from (Alvarez-Ramirez et al., 2004), leading to the controller depicted in Figure 2. Design steps are defined as follows:

- a) Linearization and factorization of the system.

The system on which our control problem is focused is linearized as follow:

$$\Delta G(s) = \alpha H_1(s) \Delta u(s) + \beta H_2(s) \Delta \omega(s) + H_3(s) \Delta R_a(s), \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta G(s)$ is the deviation of plasma glucose concentration from the equilibrium value G^* , ($\Delta G(t) := G(t) - G^*$); $\Delta u(s)$ is the deviation of insulin infusion from the equilibrium value u^* , ($\Delta u(t) := u(t) - u^*$); $\Delta \omega(s)$ is the deviation of glucagon infusion from the equilibrium value ω^* , which is null ($\Delta \omega(t) := \omega(t)$); and, $\Delta R_a(s)$ is the disturbance due to the meal intake ($\Delta R_a(t) := R_a(t)$).

Transfer functions $H_1(s)$, $H_2(s)$, and $H_3(s)$ are the linearized plants representing the glycemic effect of insulin, glucagon and meal intake respectively, with $H_1(0) = 1$, and $H_2(0) = 1$. Thus, gains α and β correspond to the insulin and glucagon sensitivities, respectively. Remark that, due to subcutaneous pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of insulin and glucagon, $H_1(s)$ will have a slower dynamics than $H_2(s)$.

In the absence of disturbance, the plant with faster dynamics (i.e., $H_2(s)$) can be factorized as follows:

$$\Delta G(s) = H_2(s) \left(\alpha \frac{H_1(s)}{H_2(s)} \Delta u(s) + \beta \Delta w(s) \right). \quad (2)$$

Defining now

$$\Delta \mu(s) := \Delta v_1(s) + \Delta v_2(s) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta v_1(s) := \alpha \frac{H_1(s)}{H_2(s)} \Delta u(s) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta v_2(s) := \beta \Delta w(s) \quad (5)$$

equation (2) can be expressed as a SISO system in terms of a new virtual control action

$$\Delta G(s) = H_2(s) \cdot \Delta \mu(s), \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta \mu(s)$ represents a “control effort” without saturation constraints, as opposed to insulin, $\Delta u(s)$, and glucagon, $\Delta w(s)$, infusion, since both signals must be non-negative.

b) Design of master controller $C(s)$ for the equivalent SISO plant.

A controller design can thus be carried out for the SISO system (6), with closed-loop dynamics given by

$$H_{cl}(s) = \frac{C(s)H_2(s)}{1 + C(s)H_2(s)} \quad (7)$$

yielding the master controller $C(s)$ in Figure 2. In this work, a PD controller

is considered

$$C(s) = \frac{\Delta\mu(s)}{G_{ref} - G(s)} = kp(1 + T_d s) \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta\mu(s) = kp(1 + T_d s) (G_{ref}(s) - G(s)) \quad (9)$$

where k_p is the proportional gain, T_d is the derivative time, and G_{ref} is the value of the glucose reference.

- c) Divisor design to distribute the total virtual control action $\Delta\mu(s)$ in both primary $\Delta v_1(s)$ and secondary $\Delta v_2(s)$ actions. 150

The control action computed in (9) can be distributed in terms of $\Delta v_1(s)$ and $\Delta v_2(s)$ with consideration of the constraint imposed by (3), i.e., both actions must add up the total control effort needed. Then, by inverting (4) and (5), the final insulin and glucagon infusions can be obtained:

$$\Delta u(s) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{H_1(s)}{H_2(s)} \right)^{-1} \Delta v_1(s), \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta w(s) = \frac{1}{\beta} \Delta v_2(s), \quad (11)$$

$$u(s) = \Delta u(s) + u^*, \quad (12)$$

$$w(s) = \Delta w(s). \quad (13)$$

For the design of the divisor that distributes the virtual control action $\Delta\mu(s)$ is

$$\Delta v_1(s) = (1 - \gamma) \Delta\mu(s), \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta v_2(s) = \gamma \Delta\mu(s). \quad (15)$$

Intuitively, insulin delivery should be prioritized with respect to glucagon. The latter should be delivered only when insulin infusion is below a given threshold, u_{th} . Thus, the following divisor is defined

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} 0 & \tilde{u}(t) > u_{th} \\ 1 & \tilde{u}(t) \leq u_{th} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Figure 2: Block diagram of the closed-loop system for glucose coordinated control based on the proposed parallel control structure.

where $\tilde{u}(t)$ is the would-be insulin infusion if directing the control effort through the insulin input channel. In the extreme case where $u_{th} = 0$, glucagon would act when the insulin pump is shut off in response to impending hypoglycemia. However, delays due to glucagon subcutaneous absorption may be a limitation to successfully avoid hypoglycemia. For this reason, $u_{th} \geq 0$ will be considered here. Remark that when $\gamma = 1$ (activation of glucagon delivery), the insulin infusion will correspond to the free response of the system (10), since $\Delta v_1(s) = 0$.

The switching due to (16) does not affect the closed-loop transfer function. When $\gamma = 0$, the closed-loop transfer function is

$$H_{cl}^0(s) := \frac{C(s) \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{H_1(s)}{H_2(s)} \right)^{-1} \alpha H_1(s)}{1 + C(s) \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{H_1(s)}{H_2(s)} \right)^{-1} \alpha H_1(s)} = \frac{C(s) H_2(s)}{1 + C(s) H_2(s)}, \quad (17)$$

and, when $\gamma = 1$:

$$H_{cl}^1(s) := \frac{C(s) \frac{1}{\beta} \beta H_2(s)}{1 + C(s) \frac{1}{\beta} \beta H_2(s)} = \frac{C(s) H_2(s)}{1 + C(s) H_2(s)}. \quad (18)$$

Therefore, the closed-loop transfer function remains unaltered and it will be stable by design conditions on $C(s)$.

2.2. Comparison between non-coordinated and coordinated control strategies.

The non-coordinated structure considered for the comparison is shown in Figure 3. In order to be consistent with the structure evaluation, the design and tuning of the insulin loop is the same as the one used in the coordinated

controller. It means that the insulin infusion is equivalent to setting $\gamma = 0$ in equations (14)-(15). Insulin infusion is saturated to be non-negative. The design of the glucagon loop is based on the proportional-derivative controller (PD) proposed in (Herrero et al., 2013), in which the proportional term only acts when glucose is below the glucose reference for the glucagon loop, $G_{ref_{ggon}}$:

$$PD_{ggon}(s) = \kappa + K_{p_{ggon}} T_{d_{ggon}} s \quad (19)$$

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} K_{p_{ggon}} & \text{if } G_{ref_{ggon}} - G > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$w(s) = PD_{ggon}(s) (G_{ref_{ggon}} - G(s)) \quad (21)$$

where PD_{ggon} is the controller transfer function, $K_{p_{ggon}}$ is the proportional gain and $T_{d_{ggon}}$ is the derivative time.

Figure 3: Block diagram of the closed-loop system for glucose non-coordinated control.

In current dual-hormone systems based on insulin and glucagon independent loops structure, an activation condition for the glucagon loop is defined. In order to evaluate the isolated contribution of the coordination in the proposed dual-hormone structure, the glucagon loop will be activated equivalently to the switching condition (16), that is

$$u_{ggon}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & u_{ins}(t) > u_{th} \\ w(t) & u_{ins}(t) \leq u_{th} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

2.3. Controllers tuning.

Both controllers, coordinated (CC) and non-coordinated (NCC) were tuned
165 through extensive simulations considering different sources of variability so as
to achieve the highest possible percentage of time in range [70,180] mg/dL and

the lowest possible percentage below target. The value of the parameters that are part of the insulin loop, i.e., k_p , T_d , G_{ref} , had the same values in both configurations in order to isolate the effects of the coordination and observe the differences between both structures and the consequences of having different hormone delivery distributions. For all the evaluated subjects, parameters were fixed to the same value except the parameters α and β (insulin and glucagon sensitivities), which were individualized for each patient following an identification procedure based on the impulse response for a set of bolus doses. It is worth mention that bolus responses can be obtained easily in an in-vivo environment. Although insulin sensitivity can be easily derived from open-loop therapy tuning, it is not the case for glucagon sensitivity. Table 1 shows the parameters values for both configurations.

Table 1: Controllers parameters.

	CC	NCC
K_p	3.1350×10^{-4}	3.1350×10^{-4}
$T_d(\text{min})$	90	90
$G_{ref}(\text{mg/dL})$	100	100
α	(*)	(*)
β	(*)	(*)
K_{pggon}	-	$0.3228/\beta$
$T_{dggon}(\text{min})$	-	10
$G_{refggon}(\text{mg/dL})$	-	90
u_{th}	(**)	(**)

(*) Patient dependent.

(**) Parameter under assessment in the present work.

The proportional gain of the glucagon loop in the NCC controller, K_{pggon} , was tuned for the average patient to get the lowest possible mean glucose without hypoglycemia and, then, it was individualized for each patient by means of his/her glucagon sensitivity, β .

It is important to note that the effect of the parameter u_{th} in the controller performance was evaluated in order to determine the optimal switch condition for the CC. The following thresholds were considered:

$$u_{th} \in \{0, 0.25u^*, 0.5u^*, 0.75u^*\}.$$

2.4. In-Silico evaluation

The UVA/Padova simulator (Dalla Man et al., 2014) with the addition of
 185 the exercise model described in (Schiavon et al., 2013) and intra-day and intra-subject variability was used to assess and compare the proposed control structures.

Intra-day variability was introduced to the simulator by modifying some of the parameters: meal variability was emulated by introducing meal-size variability (CV=10%), meal-time variability (STD=20 min) and uncertainty in
 190 the carbohydrate estimation (uniform distribution between -30% and +40%) (Brazeau et al., 2013). Variability of meal absorption rate (k_{abs}) and carbohydrate bioavailability (f) were considered to be $\pm 30\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ respectively. For intra-day meal variability, the 11 meals corresponding to the patients cohort
 195 were randomly assigned at each meal intake.

To emulate intra-subject variability, insulin absorption model parameters (k_d , k_{a1} , k_{a2}) were varied $\pm 30\%$ (Haidar et al., 2013a). Insulin sensitivity parameters (V_{mx} , K_{p3}) were assumed to change along the day following the sinusoidal pattern

$$p(t) = p_0 + 0.3 \cdot p_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{24 \cdot 60} t\right) + 2\pi \cdot RND, \quad (23)$$

where $p(t)$ is the corresponding time-varying parameter (i.e. V_{mx} or k_{p3}); p_0 is the default parameter value in the simulator; and RND is a randomly uniformly generated number between 0 and 1 (Wilinska et al., 2010).

Finally, variability was added to exercise by modifying the starting time
 200 (STD=20 min), the exercise intensity (CV=10%), and the duration (CV=10%).

Three scenarios were considered; all of them with meal announcement. Scenario A consisted in the following daily pattern of carbohydrate doses: 7am

(50g), 1pm (80g), 8pm (60g). Scenario B added a daily snack (30g) at 5pm to the scenario A in order to assess a possible superposition of glucagon and carbohydrates. Lastly, the scenario C added daily exercise to scenario A, starting at 3pm with a duration of 60 min and an intensity ($VO_{\max}\%$) of 50%.

A two-week scenarios duration was used to compare the dual-hormone control structures in 100 adults –based on the 10 adults that are available in the educational version of the UVA/Padova simulator, with 10 repetitions each getting different instances of variability. The chosen basal insulin infusion rates (u^*) were the ones provided by the simulator for each subject.

Notice that the 100 adult profiles obtained were assessed in open loop in order to check that the glucose concentration profiles during standard therapy did not include abnormalities (i.e. instability in the glucose response or parameters outside of the physiological ranges).

2.5. Data analysis

In order to carry out the comparisons, the following internationally accepted glycaemic control metrics (Maahs et al., 2016) were used: mean blood glucose (BG); percentage time in target range [70,180] mg/dL (TIR); percentage time below target ($< 70\text{mg/dL}$); percentage time below 54mg/dL ($< 54\text{mg/dL}$); percentage time above target ($> 180\text{mg/dL}$); standard deviation (STD); daily average of insulin delivered in units of insulin (INS); and daily average of glucagon delivered in mg (GGON).

The differences between the eight configurations resulting from the combination of the type of controller (CC and NCC) and the four threshold switch conditions ($u_{th} \in \{0, 0.25u^*, 0.5u^*, 0.75u^*\}$) were assessed non-parametrically due to the non-normality of the data, using the Kruskal Wallis test with Fisher’s LSD post-hoc analysis. This analysis was repeated for each scenario (A, B, and C).

230 **3. Results**

After switch condition assessment for the coordinated controller, $u_{th} = 0.75u^*$ showed the most favorable results in all considered metrics. Therefore, this threshold value was considered in our coordinated controller proposal (CC). In contrast, the threshold screening for the NCC proved that the best results
235 for this configuration was obtained for $u_{th} = 0$.

For the sake of clarity, we present the following comparisons:

- 1) Between CC and its equivalent non-coordinated control structure for the same threshold value (NCC-A), i.e., $u_{th} = 0.75u^*$.
- 2) Between CC and the NCC with $u_{th} = 0$ (NCC-B).

240 Table 2 shows the results for scenarios A, B and C, respectively. These results are presented with the mean (SD) and median [IQR].

In addition, these comparisons are also shown in Figure 4. Median and interquartile range for each scenario and controller configuration are represented for the studied cohort. Two days have been represented instead of all fourteen
245 days of the simulation in order to observe better the behaviour described by the two configurations proposed.

Across the patient cohorts, when there was only meal perturbation (scenario A), the time in hypoglycemia was the same in CC and its equivalent non-coordinated configuration, NCC-A, ($p = 0.232$ for percentage of time under 70mg/dL, and $p = 0.924$ for time under 54mg/dL) although with greater
250 glucagon infusion in NCC-A ($p < 0.001$). Nevertheless, the mean glucose and the time above range were greater in the non-coordinated configuration ($p < 0.01$) despite higher insulin delivery in NCC-A. These results reflect that, when the glucagon delivery is triggered at the same time, the NCC-A is prone
255 to glucagon and insulin over-delivery resulting in increased hyperglycemia, compared to CC.

On the other side, comparisons between the CC and the best configuration for NCC, NCC-B, showed the same performance in time in range ($p = 0.652$), and time above 180mg/dL ($p = 0.233$); but time below 70mg/dL and 54mg/dL

Figure 4: Evaluated controllers performance during scenario A, B and C. Median and percentile 25 and 75 are represented for two simulated days.

Table 2: Statistical analysis (Scenario A, B, and C).

	CC	NNC-A	NNC-B	CC vs NCC-A	CC vs NCC-B
Scenario A	MG (mg/dL)	129.04(5.55) 129[126.19; 131.63]	141.47(17.58) 137.32[134.72;139.59]	121.60(5.52) 120.71[117.33;124.59]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01
	TIR(%)	94.13(3.27) 94.49[92.11;96.78]	88.18(15.84) 92.83[89.96;96.22]	94.58(3.62) 95.57[92.37;97.61]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.652
	> 180(%)	5.73(3.35) 5.43[2.90;7.89]	11.81(15.84) 7.17[3.78;9.98]	4.53(3.53) 3.47[1.56;6.78]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.233
	< 70(%)	0.14(0.30) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.01(0.04) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.89(0.95) 0.57[0.25;1.26]	P-value 0.232 P-value < 0.01
	< 54(%)	0.00(0.02) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.00(0.00) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.06(0.13) 0.00[0.00;0.05]	P-value 0.924 P-value < 0.01
	INS (U/day)	47.43(11.52) 44.41[40.23;53.25]	52.49(12.50) 51.17[44.38;58.14]	49.10(12.12) 45.80[41.50;55.00]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.328
	GGON (mg/day)	0.64(0.54) 0.44[0.25;0.92]	2.08(2.48) 1.21[0.65; 2.16]	0.72(0.75) 0.31[0.18;1.11]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01
Scenario B	MG (mg/dL)	130.53(5.53) 130.41[128.03;132.95]	142.52(16.32) 137.99[136.03;141.60]	122.60(5.44) 121.42[118.27;126.81]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01
	TIR(%)	94.32(3.12) 94.92[92.97;96.49]	88.26(14.66) 92.77[89.93;95.45]	94.54(3.67) 95.54[92.61;97.32]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.814
	>180(%)	5.57(3.13) 5.02[3.39;7.03]	11.73(14.67) 7.23[4.55;10.07]	4.40(3.32) 3.44[1.96;5.84]	P-value 0.01 P-value 0.210
	< 70(%)	0.11(0.27) 0.00[0.00;0.11]	0.02(0.06) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	1.06(1.32) 0.60[0.15;1.38]	P-value 0.518 P-value < 0.01
	< 54(%)	0.00(0.01) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.00(0.00) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.21(0.43) 0.00[0.00;0.24]	P-value 0.968 P-value 0.01
	INS (U/day)	48.77(11.87) 45.31[41.98;54.94]	53.85(12.81) 51.96[46.07;59.76]	50.42(12.47) 46.67[43.13;56.68]	P-value 0.01 P-value 0.346
	GGON (mg/day)	0.61(0.51) 0.47[0.23;0.94]	2.01(2.35) 1.20[0.67;2.18]	0.66(0.67) 0.30[0.17;1.12]	P-value 0.01 P-value 0.734
Scenario C	MG (mg/dL)	123.26(5.72) 121.93[119.27;126.80]	136.75(18.28) 132.06[129.88;133.96]	120.04(6.84) 119.39[115.62;120.30]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01
	TIR(%)	91.56(3.42) 91.53[89.19;94.10]	89.26(15.21) 94.12[92.08;96.01]	93.15(4.32) 94.42[90.61;96.34]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.126
	> 180(%)	5.04(3.11) 4.24[2.47;6.88]	10.32(15.36) 5.43[3.15;7.56]	4.54(4.44) 2.91[1.65;5.28]	P-value 0.01 P-value 0.623
	< 70(%)	3.40(2.92) 2.89[0.95;4.84]	0.42(0.65) 0.15[0.00;0.42]	2.31(1.65) 2.12[0.84;3.52]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01
	< 54(%)	0.73(1.29) 0.15[0.00;0.72]	0.02(0.07) 0.00[0.00;0.00]	0.36(1.43) 0.24[0.00;0.58]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.603
	INS (U/day)	46.53(11.22) 44.02[39.26;52.23]	51.48(12.13) 50.61[43.44;56.77]	48.67(11.70) 46.38[41.27;54.15]	P-value < 0.01 P-value 0.194
	GGON (mg/day)	0.96(0.79) 0.69[0.36;1.71]	2.64(3.11) 1.47[0.78;3.52]	1.38(1.39) 0.83[0.43;2.37]	P-value < 0.01 P-value < 0.01

260 were lower in CC ($p < 0.01$ in both cases). The hormone delivery was the same for insulin ($p = 0.328$), but it was greater for glucagon in NCC-B ($p < 0.01$). It means that the different way to distribute the glucagon delivery of CC resulted in a reduced time in hypoglycaemia.

With the addition of a snack perturbation (scenario B), the number of hypoglycemic events increased relative to scenario A for NCC-B, and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) with respect to CC controller, which showed to be most favourable. Glucagon and insulin delivery were the same in both ($p = 0.346$ for insulin delivery, and $p = 0.734$ for the glucagon delivery), although the performance was sub-optimal in NCC-B configuration. However, the percentage of time in hypoglycemia was statistically similar in CC and NCC-A, although it was at the expense of a higher time in hyperglycemia in NCC-A ($p < 0.01$), a higher glucose means and variability ($p < 0.01$ in both), and a higher hormones delivery ($p < 0.01$ in glucagon and insulin delivery). Therefore, the CC configuration showed improved performance.

275 Lastly, when exercise perturbation was added (scenario C), CC and NCC-A configurations performed similarly as in scenario A although the number of hypoglycemic events increased. Nevertheless, the amount of glucagon was significantly higher in NCC-A ($p < 0.001$) and the percentile 75 was further of the physiological acceptable limit (1mg/day). If the best configuration for NCC is considered for the comparison, the glucagon delivery was improved but it was even greater ($p < 0.01$) compared with CC configuration whereas the insulin delivery was statistically similar ($p = 0.346$). These behaviours confirmed the positive benefit of the intrinsic coordination in hormones delivery of the CC configuration.

285 Overall, from the obtained results, the comparison of the CC with its non-coordinated equivalent structure, NCC-A, proved that the coordinated structure handled better with the hormones deliveries since CC was able to keep the glucose mean closer to the glucose reference without increasing of hypoglycaemia events in the meal and exercise scenarios.

290 Additionally, CC achieved a higher time in range and a significant reduc-

tion of the glycemic variability. When considering which is the best controller proposal for the non-coordinated controllers (CC vs NCC-B), the CC controller still showed better performance in terms of percentage of time in hypoglycaemia during meal and snack scenarios whereas it also presented an improved usage of glucagon in meal and exercise scenarios, while being similar in the snack scenario.

4. Conclusions

The coordinated control structure proposed is a representation of the cooperative behavior between alpha and beta cells of the pancreas. Results show that a timely glucagon delivery when the system starts to reduce insulin infusion below basal values improved the performance of CC. Additionally, an optimized usage of both hormones achieving the best possible results compared to non-coordinated structure is demonstrated.

The coordinated configuration deals with the overlapping between glucagon and carbs and with the severe hypoglycaemia. However, the time in hypoglycaemia during exercise scenarios could be further improved.

The hypoglycemia should not be solved with an over-delivery of glucagon to avoid potential secondary effects to the patient. Therefore, glucagon must be delivered in an optimal amount, a requirement which the NCC structure is far from accomplishing.

The coordinated configuration, compared with the non-coordinated one, presents a better performance with a reduction of glycaemic variability in the most demanding scenario, and glucagon delivery inside of the acceptable healthy limits.

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